

Using the Kalman Filter for SLAM

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$$p(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{m} | \mathbf{Z}^{k-1}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{m} | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \mathbf{m} | \mathbf{Z}^{k-1}) d\mathbf{x}_{k-1}$$

Contents

- Trivial Kinematics
- Rapid sweep over localisation and mapping (components of SLAM)
- Basic EKF Feature Based SLAM
- Feature types and representations
- Implementation
- Convergence Properties
- Pose Based SLAM
- Sparse Inverse Pose Based Formulation

Vehicle Models - Prediction

$$\underline{\mathbf{x}_v(k+1)} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_v(k), \mathbf{u}(k)); \quad \mathbf{u}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} V(k) \\ \phi(k) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_v(k+1) \\ y_v(k+1) \\ \theta_v(k+1) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_v(k) + \delta T V(k) \cos(\theta_v(k)) \\ y_v(k) + \delta T V(k) \sin(\theta_v(k)) \\ \theta_v(k) + \frac{\delta T V(k) \tan(\phi(k))}{L} \end{bmatrix}$$

Noise is in control....

$$\underline{\mathbf{u}(k)} = \underline{\mathbf{u}_n(k)} + \mathbf{v}(k)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_n(k)$ is a nominal (intended) control signal and $\mathbf{v}(k)$ is a zero mean gaussian distributed noise vector:

$$\underline{\mathbf{v}(k)} \sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_V^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_\phi^2 \end{bmatrix}\right)$$
$$\underline{\mathbf{u}(k)} \sim \mathcal{N}\left(\underline{\mathbf{u}_n(k)}, \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_V^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_\phi^2 \end{bmatrix}\right)$$

Effect of control noise on uncertainty:

$$\underline{\mathbf{x}}_v(k|k-1) = \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k-1|k-1), \mathbf{u}(k), k)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_v(k|k-1) = \nabla \mathbf{F}_x \mathbf{P}_v(k-1|k-1) \nabla \mathbf{F}_x^T + \nabla \mathbf{F}_v \mathbf{Q} \nabla \mathbf{F}_v^T$$

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_v^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_\phi^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\nabla \mathbf{F}_x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -\delta TV \sin(\theta_v) \\ 0 & 1 & \delta TV \cos(\theta_v) \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\nabla \mathbf{F}_u = \begin{bmatrix} \delta T \cos(\theta_v) & 0 \\ \delta T \sin(\theta_v) & 0 \\ \frac{\tan(\phi)}{L} & \frac{\delta TV \sec^2(\phi)}{L} \end{bmatrix}$$

Using Dead-Reckoned Data

Navigation Architecture

Background T-Composition

$$\mathbf{x}_{i,k} = \mathbf{x}_{i,j} \oplus \mathbf{x}_{j,k}$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{j,i} = \ominus \mathbf{x}_{i,j}$$

Compounding transformations

Just functions!

$$\mathbf{x}_1 \oplus \mathbf{x}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 + x_2 \cos \theta_1 - y_2 \sin \theta_1 \\ y_1 + x_2 \sin \theta_1 + y_2 \cos \theta_1 \end{bmatrix}$$
$$\ominus \mathbf{x}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -x_1 \cos \theta_1 - y_1 \sin \theta_1 \\ x_1 \sin \theta_1 - y_1 \cos \theta_1 \\ -\theta_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{J}_1(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \triangleq \frac{\partial(\mathbf{x}_1 \oplus \mathbf{x}_2)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_1}$$
$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -x_2 \sin \theta_1 - y_2 \cos \theta_1 \\ 0 & 1 & x_2 \cos \theta_1 - y_2 \sin \theta_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$
$$\mathbf{J}_2(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \triangleq \frac{\partial(\mathbf{x}_1 \oplus \mathbf{x}_2)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_2}$$
$$= \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_1 & -\sin \theta_1 & 0 \\ \sin \theta_1 & \cos \theta_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Deduce an Incremental Move

These can be in massive error

$$\mathbf{u}(k) = \ominus \mathbf{x}_o(k-1) \oplus \mathbf{x}_o(k)$$

But the common error is subtracted out here

Use this “move” as a control

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\mathbf{x}_v(k+1)} &= \mathbf{f}(\underline{\mathbf{x}_v(k)}, \underline{\mathbf{u}(k)}) \\ &= \underline{\mathbf{x}_v(k)} \oplus \underbrace{(\ominus \mathbf{x}_o(k-1) \oplus \mathbf{x}_o(k))}_{dr\text{-control}} \\ &= \underline{\mathbf{x}_v(k)} \oplus \underline{\mathbf{u}_o(k)}\end{aligned}$$

Substitution into Prediction equation (using J1 and J2 as Jacobians):

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{P}(k|k-1) &= \nabla \mathbf{F}_x \mathbf{P}_v(k-1|k-1) \nabla \mathbf{F}_x^T + \nabla \mathbf{F}_v \mathbf{Q} \nabla \mathbf{F}_v^T \\ &= \mathbf{J}_1(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}_o) \underline{\mathbf{P}_v(k-1|k-1)} \mathbf{J}_1(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}_o)^T + \mathbf{J}_2(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}_o) \mathbf{U}_o \mathbf{J}_2(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}_o)^T\end{aligned}$$

Diagonal covariance matrix (3x3) of error in \mathbf{u}_o

Feature Based Mapping and Navigation

Look at the code!!

Problem Space

Landmarks / Features

Things that stand out to a sensor:

Corners, windows, walls, bright patches, texture...

- We shall initially proceed by considering only point features
- We'll discuss other feature types later

Three Inference Problem

Input is measurements conditioned on map and vehicle

$$\text{Data: } p(\mathbf{Z}^k | \mathbf{M}, \mathbf{x}_v)$$

We want to use Bayes' rule to “invert” this and get maps and vehicles given measurements.

Problem 1 – inferring location given a map (easy) —

Problem 2 – inferring a map given a location (easy) —

Problem 3 – SLAM – learning a map and locating simultaneously

We can use a KF for all the above

Simple Motion Model

Plant Model

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) = \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k-1|k-1) \oplus (\ominus \mathbf{x}_o(k-1) \oplus \mathbf{x}_o(k))$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) = \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k-1|k-1) \oplus \mathbf{u}_o(k)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}(k|k-1) &= \nabla \mathbf{F}_x \mathbf{P}(k-1|k-1) \nabla \mathbf{F}_x^T + \nabla \mathbf{F}_v \mathbf{Q} \nabla \mathbf{F}_v^T \\ &= \mathbf{J}_1(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}_o) \mathbf{P}_v(k-1|k-1) \mathbf{J}_1(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}_o)^T + \mathbf{J}_2(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}_o) \mathbf{U}_o \mathbf{J}_2(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}_o)^T \end{aligned}$$

Remember:

\mathbf{u} is control, \mathbf{J} 's are a fancy way of writing jacobians (composition operator). \mathbf{U} is strength of noise in plant model.

Observation Model

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}(k) &\triangleq \begin{bmatrix} r \\ \theta \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(k), \mathbf{w}(k)) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{(x_i - x_v(k))^2 + (y_i - y_v(k))^2} \\ \text{atan2}\left(\frac{y_i - y_v(k)}{x_i - x_v(k)}\right) - \theta_v \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

We differentiate w.r.t \mathbf{x}_v to arrive at the observation model jacobian:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}} &\triangleq \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{x_i - x_v(k)}{r} & \frac{y_i - y_v(k)}{r} & 0 \\ \frac{y_i - y_v(k)}{r^2} & -\frac{x_i - x_v(k)}{r^2} & -1 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Example

No features seen here

Example Code Provided

Location Covariance

Location Innovation

Problem II - Mapping

Key Point: State Vector GROWS!

New, bigger map

Old map

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(k|k)^* &= \mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}(k|k), \mathbf{z}(k), \mathbf{x}_v(k|k)) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(k|k) \\ \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(k), \mathbf{z}(k), \mathbf{x}_v(k|k)) \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(k|k) \\ x_v + r \cos(\theta + \theta_v) \\ y_v + r \sin(\theta + \theta_v) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Obs of new feature

“State augmentation”

where the coordinates of the new feature are given by the function \mathbf{g} :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{fnew} &= \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(k), \mathbf{z}(k), \mathbf{x}_v(k|k)) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} x_v + r \cos(\theta + \theta_v) \\ y_v + r \sin(\theta + \theta_v) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

→ The state vector is the map

How is **P** augmented?

Simple! Use the transformation of covariance rule..

$$\underline{\mathbf{b} = f(\mathbf{a})}$$

$$\underline{\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\mathbf{b}}\tilde{\mathbf{b}}^T\}} = \underline{\nabla \mathbf{Y} \mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\mathbf{a}}\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^T\} \nabla \mathbf{Y}^T}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(k|k)^* &= \mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}(k|k), \mathbf{z}(k), \mathbf{x}_v(k|k)) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(k|k) \\ \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(k), \mathbf{z}(k), \mathbf{x}_v(k|k)) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

G is the feature
initialisation function

$$\underline{\mathbf{P}(k|k)^*} = \nabla \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}(k|k) & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R} \end{bmatrix} \nabla \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}}^T$$

$$\nabla \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n \times n} & \mathbf{0}_{n \times 2} \\ \underbrace{\nabla \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{x}}}_{\text{0 for mapping case}} & \nabla \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{z}} \end{bmatrix}$$

Leading to :

$$\mathbf{x}(k|k)^* = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(k|k) \\ x_v + r \cos(\theta + \theta_v) \\ y_v + r \sin(\theta + \theta_v) \end{bmatrix}$$

Angle from Veh to feature

Vehicle orientation

$$\mathbf{P}(k|k)^* = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}(k|k) & 0 \\ 0 & \nabla \mathbf{G}_z \mathbf{R} \nabla \mathbf{G}_z^T \end{bmatrix}$$

So what are models h and f?

h is a function of the feature being observed:

$$\nabla \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{bmatrix} \underbrace{\dots 0 \dots}_{\text{other features}} & \underbrace{\nabla \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}_f}}_{\text{observed feature}} & \underbrace{\dots 0 \dots}_{\text{other features}} \end{bmatrix}$$

f is simply the identity transformation :

$$\mathbf{x}(k+1|k)_{map} = \mathbf{x}(k|k)_{map}$$

$$\nabla \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{I}_{n,n}$$

Turn the handle on the EKF:

All hail the Oracle ! How do we know what feature we are observing?

Problem III SLAM

“Build a map and use it at the same time”

“This a cornerstone of autonomy”

Basic S.S.C SLAM

A union of Localisation and Mapping

State vector has vehicle AND map

Why naïve? Computation!

Prediction:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v(k+1) \\ \mathbf{x}_{f,1}(k) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_{f,n}(k) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v(k) \oplus \mathbf{u}(k) \\ \mathbf{x}_{f,1}(k) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_{f,n}(k) \end{bmatrix}$$

← Vehicle Moves
← Map remains unchanged

$$\nabla \mathbf{F}_x = \begin{bmatrix} \nabla \mathbf{F}_{x_v} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_{2n \times 2n} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{J1}(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}) & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_{2n \times 2n} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\nabla \mathbf{F}_u = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{J2}(\mathbf{x}_v, \mathbf{u}) & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0}_{2n \times 2n} \end{bmatrix}$$

We have all the terms needed for prediction step

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{x}(k|k-1) &= f(\mathbf{x}(k|k), (\overbrace{\mathbf{u}(k)}^{\text{control}} + \overbrace{\mathbf{v}(k)}^{\text{noise}})) \\
 \mathbf{P}(k|k-1) &= \nabla \mathbf{F}_x \mathbf{P}(k-1|k-1) \nabla \mathbf{F}_x^T + \nabla \mathbf{F}_v \mathbf{U} \nabla \mathbf{F}_v^T
 \end{aligned}$$

Feature Initialisation:

$$\underline{\mathbf{x}(k|k)^*} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(k|k) \\ x_v + r \cos(\theta + \theta_v) \\ y_v + r \sin(\theta + \theta_v) \end{bmatrix} \leftarrow \text{This is } y(.)$$

These two lines
are g()

$$\underline{\mathbf{P}(k|k)^*} = \nabla \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{x},\mathbf{z}} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}(k|k) & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{R} \end{bmatrix} \nabla \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{x},\mathbf{z}}^T$$

$$\nabla \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{x},\mathbf{z}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n \times n} & \mathbf{0}_{n \times 2} \\ \underbrace{\nabla \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{x}}}_{\text{now non-zero}} & \nabla \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{z}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n \times n} & \mathbf{0}_{n \times 2} \\ [\nabla \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{x}_v} \cdots \mathbf{0} \cdots] & \nabla \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{z}} \end{bmatrix}$$

This a step only runs if a new feature is seen

Observation Model

We have all the terms needed for update step

Feature Types

- In theory we can use any geometric parameterisation
- In practice you need to be very careful about a choice of parameterisation.

If ρ is large small errors in θ do crazy things!

Much smarter to use SPMMap (Tardos) which represents geometry and uncertainty in frames centred on a feature. Also see Kai Arras's PhD as an excellent SPMMap resource

The SPMAP

Closed Loop of Transformations

$$0 = \mathbf{B}_{f,e}[\ominus \mathbf{x}_{w,f} \oplus \mathbf{x}_{w,r} \oplus \mathbf{x}_{r,s} \oplus \mathbf{x}_{s,e}]$$

This is the
observation
model for every
feature type!

Symmetry Selection

Measurement to Feature Transformation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{0} &= \mathbf{B}_{f,e} [\ominus \mathbf{x}_{w,f} \oplus \mathbf{x}_{w,r} \oplus \mathbf{x}_{r,s} \oplus \mathbf{x}_{s,e}] \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{f,e} \end{aligned}$$

measurement

robot

World

Only the Δx and $\Delta \theta$ components of $\mathbf{x}_{f,e}$ matter

Calculating EKF Jacobians

Differentiating with respect to feature location

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \Psi(\cdot)}{\partial \mathbf{p}_f} &= \mathbf{B}_{f,e} \times \frac{\partial \Psi(\cdot)}{\partial [\ominus \mathbf{B}_{f,f}^T \mathbf{p}_f]} \times \frac{\partial [\ominus \mathbf{B}_{f,f}^T \mathbf{p}_f]}{\partial [\mathbf{B}_{f,f}^T \mathbf{p}_f]} \times \frac{\partial [\mathbf{B}_{f,f}^T \mathbf{p}_f]}{\partial \mathbf{p}_f} \\
 &= \mathbf{B}_{f,e} \times \mathbf{J}_1 \{ \ominus \mathbf{B}_{f,f}^T \mathbf{p}_f, \mathbf{x}_{f,e} \} \times \mathbf{J}_{\ominus} \{ \mathbf{B}_{f,f}^T \mathbf{p}_f \} \times \mathbf{B}_{f,f}^T \\
 &= -\mathbf{B}_{f,e} \times \mathbf{J}_1 \{ \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{x}_{f,e} \} \times \mathbf{B}_{f,f}^T
 \end{aligned}$$

Common term X_{fe} : how does Observation appear in feature frame?

similarly with respect to robot center

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \Psi(\cdot)}{\partial \mathbf{p}_r} &= \mathbf{B}_{f,e} \times \frac{\partial \Psi(\cdot)}{\partial [\mathbf{J}_{e,r} \mathbf{B}_{r,r}^T \mathbf{p}_r]} \times \frac{\partial [\mathbf{J}_{e,r} \mathbf{B}_{r,r}^T \mathbf{p}_r]}{\partial [\mathbf{B}_{r,r}^T \mathbf{p}_r]} \times \frac{\partial [\mathbf{B}_{r,r}^T \mathbf{p}_r]}{\partial \mathbf{p}_r} \\
 &\vdots \\
 &= \mathbf{B}_{f,e} \times \mathbf{J}_2 \{ \mathbf{x}_{f,e}, \mathbf{0} \} \times \mathbf{J}_{e,r} \times \mathbf{B}_{r,r}^T
 \end{aligned}$$

and finally with respect to observation vector

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \Psi(\cdot)}{\partial \mathbf{p}_e} &= \mathbf{B}_{f,e} \times \frac{\partial \Psi(\cdot)}{\partial [\mathbf{B}_{e,e}^T \mathbf{p}_e]} \times \frac{\partial [\mathbf{B}_{e,e}^T \mathbf{p}_e]}{\partial [\mathbf{B}_{e,e}^T \mathbf{p}_e]} \\
 &\vdots \\
 &= \mathbf{B}_{f,e} \times \mathbf{J}_2 \{ \mathbf{x}_{f,e}, \mathbf{0} \} \times \mathbf{B}_{e,e}^T
 \end{aligned}$$

SLAM in action

SPMap Formulation

Atlas – Extending the EKF Using Multiple Frame

- Mapping MIT's “Infinite Corridor”
- 2.2 km driven path

In collaboration with M. Bosse (PhD Thesis) Prof. J. Leonard and Prof. S. Teller (MIT)

The Convergence and Stability of SLAM

By analysing the behaviour of the LG-KF we can learn about the governing properties of the SLAM problem – which are actually completely intuitive.....

We can show that:

- The determinant of any submatrix of the map covariance matrix decreases monotonically as observations are successively made.
- In the limit as the number of observations increases, the landmark estimates become fully correlated.
- In the limit, the covariance associated with any single landmark location estimate is determined only by the initial covariance in the vehicle location estimate.

$$\begin{aligned}\det \mathbf{P}(k+1|k+1) &= \det[\mathbf{P}(k+1|k) - \mathbf{W}_i(k+1)\mathbf{S}_i(k+1)\mathbf{W}^T(k+1)] \\ &\leq \det \mathbf{P}(k+1|k)\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Any principal submatrix of a *psd* matrix is also *psd* Thus,

$$\det \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k+1|k+1) \leq \det \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k+1|k) \quad (2)$$

From the prediction equations (features don't change)

$$\mathbf{P}(k+1|k) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_v \mathbf{P}_{vv}(k|k) \mathbf{F}_v^T + \mathbf{Q}_{vv} & \mathbf{F}_v \mathbf{P}_{vm}(k|k) \\ \mathbf{P}_{vm}^T(k|k) \mathbf{F}_v^T & \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k|k) \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$\det \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k+1|k+1) \leq \det \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k|k). \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{ii}^2(k+1|k+1) \leq \sigma_{ii}^2(k|k).$$

where σ_{ii}^2 is a diagonal element of \mathbf{P}_{mm}

As the number of observations taken tends to infinity a lower limit on the map covariance limit will be reached such that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} [\mathbf{P}_{mm}(k+1|k+1)] = \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k|k) \quad (1)$$

Writing $\mathbf{P}(k+1|k)$ as \mathbf{P}^\ominus and $\mathbf{P}(k+1|k+1)$ as \mathbf{P}^\oplus for notational clarity the update for the map can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k+1|k+1) &= \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k+1|k) - \mathbf{M}_2 \mathbf{S}_i^{-1} \mathbf{M}_2^T \\ &= \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k|k) - \mathbf{M}_2 \mathbf{S}_i^{-1} \mathbf{M}_2^T \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\mathbf{M}_2 = -\mathbf{P}_{vm}^\ominus \mathbf{H}_v^T + \mathbf{P}_{mm}^\ominus \mathbf{H}_{pi}^T \quad (3)$$

In the limit then $\mathbf{M}_2 \mathbf{S}_i^{-1} \mathbf{M}_2^T = \mathbf{0}$ which implies that $\mathbf{M}_2 = \mathbf{0}$

$$\mathbf{P}_{mm}(k|k) \mathbf{H}_{pi}^T = \mathbf{P}_{vm}(k|k) \mathbf{H}_v^T \quad \forall i \quad (1)$$

this holds for all i and therefore the block columns of \mathbf{P}_{mm} are linearly dependent and therefore

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} [\det \mathbf{P}_{mm}(k|k)] = 0 \quad (2)$$

Consider now the relative position between any two landmarks \mathbf{p}_i and \mathbf{p}_j of the same type.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d} &= \hat{\mathbf{p}}_i - \hat{\mathbf{p}}_j \\ &= \mathbf{G}_{ij} \mathbf{x} \end{aligned}$$

The covariance \mathbf{P}_d of \mathbf{d} is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_d &= \mathbf{G}_{ij} \mathbf{P} \mathbf{G}_{ij}^T \\ &= \mathbf{P}_{ii} + \mathbf{P}_{jj} - \mathbf{P}_{ij} - \mathbf{P}_{ij}^T \end{aligned}$$

With similar landmarks types, $\mathbf{H}_{pi} = \mathbf{H}_{pj}$ and so Equation ?? implies that the block columns of \mathbf{P}_{mm} are identical. Furthermore, because \mathbf{P}_{mm} is symmetric it follows that

$$\mathbf{P}_{ii} = \mathbf{P}_{jj} = \mathbf{P}_{ij} = \mathbf{P}_{ij}^T \quad \forall i, j \quad (3)$$

Therefore, in the limit, $\mathbf{P}_d = \mathbf{0}$ and the relationship between the landmarks is known with complete certainty.

To be Tattooed on Inside of Eyelids

- The entire structure of the SLAM problem critically depends on maintaining complete knowledge of the cross correlation between landmark estimates. Minimizing or ignoring cross correlations is precisely contrary to the structure of the problem.
- As the vehicle progresses through the environment the errors in the estimates of any pair of landmarks become more and more correlated, and indeed never become less correlated.
- In the limit, the errors in the estimates of any pair of landmarks becomes fully correlated. This means that given the exact location of any one landmark, the location of any other landmark in the map can also be determined with absolute certainty.
- As the vehicle moves through the environment taking observations of individual landmarks, the error in the estimates of the relative location between different landmarks reduces monotonically to the point where the map of relative locations is known with absolute precision.
- As the map converges in the above manner, the error in the absolute location of every landmark (and thus the whole map) reaches a lower bound determined only by the error that existed when the first observation was made.
(We didn't prove this here. However it is an excellent test for consistency in new SLAM algorithms)

This is all under the assumption that we observe all features equally often...